

SoildiverAgro project

Adoption of new management practices to increase crop production and quality

THE WHAT AND WHY

Application of biofertilizer to improve wheat yields, water and nutrient availability

The southeast of Spain is confronted with some challenges due to high pH and low rainfall, which has resulted in limited nutrient availability, affecting wheat cultivation. Crop yields are reduced as a result. Wheat agriculture in the area is extensive in terms of machinery and pesticide use, with minimal fertilization and no rotation, except for fallow periods to prevent soil depletion. The main objective of this case study is to use novel strategies based on rotations and use formulations based on microorganisms to increase nutrient availability and water retention while reducing the frequency of crop-related disease in the soil and increasing grain production. Four plots (22 x 500 m) were

selected in “Finca La Junquera” located in Caravaca (Murcia, SE Spain). The crop was implemented from December 2021 to July 2022, it was the second cycle of the rotation. Four treatments were applied: a) F100 (typical fertilization- based on pig slurry end organic-pellet); b) BA+FU (nutrient solubilizing biological bacteria and fungi+ 30% fertilization reduction); c) BA (nutrient solubilizing bacteria + 30% fertilization reduction); d) F70 (fertilization reduction). Fertilization reduction in treatment plots had no effect on wheat yield. There were no statistically significant differences in grain-specific weight between the four treatments.

1. Wheat plantation in Mediterranean South region (Spain).

KEYWORDS

Biofertilizers, wheat yield, water availability, nutrient availability, pig slurry, organic-pellet.

AUTHORSHIP

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